

A SCALE DEVELOPMENT STUDY FOR MEASURING PERCEPTIONS OF TEACHER COMPETENCY IN COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Community engagement is an essential competency in holistic teaching. As much as it is a specific domain articulated with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers, there remains to be a gap in terms of fully measuring how well teachers fair in this aspect. As such, this study proposes a scale instrument for teacher's own self-assessment on how well they demonstrate the different components of community engagement within their classrooms and their school communities. The pilot study data is analyzed using descriptive statistics and factor analysis to see how well respondents rate themselves against action statements, check the reliability of the instrument, examine the underlying factors that measure perceptions on teacher's community engagement, and identify recommendations for further improvement. Given these, results showed that a scale for teacher's self-assessment on community engagement should include five factors: (1) technical skills, (2) professionalism, (3) social awareness, (4) resource generation, and (5) pedagogical skills.

Keywords: *Community engagement; teacher competency; self-assessment; scale development; factor analysis*

INTRODUCTION

Defining Community Engagement as a Construct

Community engagement as a construct embodies collective action towards a shared goal. The United Nations Children’s Fund (UNICEF) (2020) had defined community engagement as “a foundational action for working with traditional, community, civil society, government, and opinion groups and leaders; and expanding collective or group roles in addressing the issues that affect their lives.” (p. 6.) Elrich (2000 cited in Miller, Mehta, and McCauley, 2018) defined it as “working to make a difference in communities through individual or collective action actions designed to improve the quality of life” (p. vi). Both these definitions show an encompassing applicability of the construct to different social structures that allow for organization, mobilization, and capacity-building to achieve objectives set for a community’s greater good. Applied to the context of education, community engagement was defined by the Queensland Government (n.d.) in their publication *Advancing Partnership – Parents and Community engagement Framework* to “refer to the establishment of sustainable relationships with the local community to improve student’s learning and wellbeing outcomes and assist students to understand their role in the broader community.”

It can be argued that teachers play a crucial role as an agent of engaging the community. Sanders (2003) explains that “community involvement in school is an opportunity for a more democratic and participatory approach to school functioning – one that can serve and enhance students’ achievement and well-being, build stronger schools, assist families, and revitalize communities” (p. 173). Teachers’ engagement with the school community is crucial not only in terms of resource generation, but more importantly, in building partnerships that would enable students to genuinely bridge classroom learning to the greater community. As such, it is important to understand how teachers perceive their own competency in demonstrating community engagement.

A quick review of literature shows that there is an existing gap in the discourse of identifying teacher competencies focused on community engagement, especially in the local context. Much has been written on the process of recognizing key competencies that makes community engagement successful in the general setting of community organizations and training programs, but rarely in the context of teachers and their school communities. Below is a table summarizing the different aspects of community engagement competencies from different resources:

Miller, Mehta, and McCauley (2018)	Atilas, 2018	UNICEF, 2020	Srinivas, Meenan, Drogin, DePrince (2015)	Queensland Government (n.d.)
Factors for Community Engagement 1. Personal Development	Core Competencies: 1. Program planning and implementation	Common Minimum Standards: 1. Participation 2. Empowerment and ownership	Dimensions of Measuring Community Organization Perceptions of	Elements of Parent and Community Engagement Framework 1. Communication

<p>that includes improved problem-solving, decision-making, communication skills, and an increases sense of self-efficacy (Petray and Halbert, 2013)</p> <p>2. Social Responsibility is the ability to feel concerned about the welfare of others and to act on those concerns (Olney and Grande, 1995).</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Communication skills 3. Leadership 4. Education and information technology 5. Diversity, pluralism, and multiculturalism 6. Professionalism 7. Extension and organizational management 8. Program evaluation and research 9. Technical expertise 10. Collaborative learning 11. Systems thinking 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Inclusion 4. Communication 5. Adaptability and localization 6. Building on local capacity 	<p>Partnership Benefits and Costs</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Overall experience 2. Social capital 3. Skills and competencies 4. Motivation and commitment 5. Personal growth and self-concept 6. Knowledge 7. Organizational operations 8. Organizational resources 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Partnership with parents 3. Community collaboration 4. Decision-making 5. School culture
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In the Philippine context, the implementation of DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017 or the National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Standards for Teachers (PPST) set the motion for standardizing the professional competencies of teachers across different career stages. Community engagement is subsumed under its sixth domain. Domain 6: Community Linkages and Professional Engagement states that:

[Teachers need to] establish school-community partnerships aimed at enriching the learning environment, as well as the community's engagement in the educative process. They identify and respond to opportunities that link teaching and learning in the classroom to the experiences, interests and aspirations of the wider school community and other key stakeholders. They understand and fulfill their obligations in upholding professional ethics, accountability and transparency to promote professional and harmonious relationships with learners, parents, schools and the wider community (p. 5).

To further elaborate the expected competencies to be demonstrated by beginning teachers in their induction stage, below is a table from PPST's Domain 6 strands:

STRANDS
<p>Strand 6.1</p> <p>Establishment of learning environment that are responsive to community context</p>
<p>Strand 6.2</p> <p>Engagement of parents and the wider school community in the educative process</p>
<p>Strand 6.3</p> <p>Professional ethics</p>

Central to establishing the importance of developing a local scale that measures teachers' perceptions on their community engagement competencies is the observed misalignment of the Result-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) Key Results Area (KRA) with the specificities of PPST Domain 6. Despite the articulation on the importance of collaboration and professional communities on the RPMS Tool rationale, its design fails to identify how the required means of verification (MOV) contribute to its desired goal. Of the 13 objectives under the five KRAs, the Classroom Observation Tool (COT) is listed as the main MOV for nine objectives. Even without an overt ruling, there appears to be a bias on measuring teacher effectiveness in his or her capacity to deliver instructions inside the classroom. This may divert the attention and effort of teachers to concentrate on improving skills such as classroom management, differentiating instructions, and measuring student progress instead of holistically focusing on their strengths and areas of growth spread across the seven domains of the PPST. Thus, the RPMS tool does not fully measure how community linkages and professional engagement competence of teachers are being developed. It is therefore helpful to develop a scale where teachers can do self-ratings and reflection on their own performances anchored on behavioral indicators for community engagement.

RESEARCH QUESTION

This study aimed to identify key factors that affect teacher's own perceptions of their competency for community engagement by piloting a proposed scale instrument to assess the construct.

The goals of the pilot testing were to:

1. gather descriptive statistics on how the respondents rated themselves based on community engagement action statements,
2. check the reliability of the instrument,
3. examine the underlying factors that measure perceptions on teachers' community engagement, and
4. identify recommendations for further scale development.

METHODOLOGY

Prototyping the Instrument

In line with the present challenges posed by the infancy of PPST and RPMS in measuring all the aspects of teacher competency, a proposed scale for measuring teacher perceptions on their own competencies on engaging the community is prototyped based on the common categories listed from the quick literature review and the standards

outlined by PPST Domain 6. These categories are further fleshed out by operationalizing behavioral indicators that make the dimensions of the community engagement construct more tangible and observable. The identified behavioral indicators are then converted into action statements. There are seven initial categories that define community engagement in the context of teaching in the Philippines: (1) systems thinking, (2) personal effectiveness, (3) collaboration with stakeholders, (4) communication skills, (5) project management skills, (6) empowerment, and (7) professionalism. These were derived by thematically bucketing similar denominators from the literature review. Below is a construct diagram that deconstructs community engagement to its common categories to behavioral indicators and its corresponding action statements:

These 21 action statements were then randomly arranged in a survey instrument that asks teacher respondents to do a self-rating on a 5-point Likert Scale (1 for Strongly Disagree to 5 for Strongly Agree) on how well they demonstrated the action statements last School Year 2019 – 2020.

RESULTS

Analyzing the Survey- Generated Data

Majority of the 23 respondents taught in public schools (15 of 23 or 65.22%) and most of them had a total teaching experience that fell within the 1-5 years category group (15 of 23 or 65.22%). There is a distributed teaching assignment response that shows that there are 8 of 23 who are teaching in the elementary level (34.78%), 7 of 23 (30.43%) who are teaching in junior high school, 7 of 23 (30.43%) who are teaching in senior high school, and 1 respondent teaching at the kinder level (4.35%). The demographic profile descriptive statistics breakdown can be found on Appendix A. Below is a graphical representation of the demographic profile of the 23 teacher respondents who voluntarily answered the survey.

Participant Demographic Based on School Type

Participant Demographic Based on Teaching Assignment

Participant Demographic Based on Years of Service

Using the mean range and verbal interpretation table below, the 4.24 mean of all the 23 participants for all the items in the survey fall under the Agree category.

Weight/ Scale	Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.51 – 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.51 – 4.50	Agree
3	2.51 – 3.50	Neither Agree nor Disagree
2	1.51 – 2.50	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree

This shows that in general, the respondents agree that they were able to demonstrate the action statements listed in the instrument. The breakdown of the descriptive statistic for average of the whole instrument is found on Appendix C. Below is a histogram that shows the approximate distribution of all the participants' score mean:

Histogram of All Item Mean

In terms of identifying the individual action statements that had the highest and lowest means for the participants, the data showed Question 7 on adherence to professional ethics (4.74), Question 21 on transparency and accountability (4.65), and Question 2 on self-efficacy for positive community contribution (4.65) fall within the Strongly Agree verbal interpretation. This may mean that these are the aspects of community engagement that the sample population feels most confident in demonstrating. On the other hand, Question 12 on technical skills on project management (3.96), Question 18 on sustaining communication exchanges (3.96), Question 13 on inspiring others (3.96), Question 13 on sustainability (3.74), and Question 19 on resource generation (3.52) are the three lowest-ranked action statements which fall under the verbal interpretation of Agree. Despite having been interpreted as agreeable statements in reflecting about own community engagement competency, it may be argued that the lowest-ranked action statements also show training needs that should be given focus during in-service trainings. The breakdown for each item's descriptive statistics is found on Appendix B. Below is a summary of the mean for each of the questions that had the highest and lowest mean for the sample population.

QUESTION NUMBER	N	Mean	Rank
7. I abide by the professional code of ethics in fulfilling my responsibilities to the school community.	23	4.74	1
21. I am transparent and accountable for all my actions.	23	4.65	3
2. I believe that I can positively contribute to the community by using my skills and applying my professional training as an educator.	23	4.65	3
QUESTION NUMBER	N	Mean	Rank
12. I am able to effectively plan, execute, and evaluate a school community activity or project.	23	3.96	17
18. I am able to solicit feedback and sustain communications with partners regarding community concerns and projects.	23	3.96	17
20. I inspire other people to initiate and join in activities and projects for the school community.	23	3.96	17
13. I plan for the sustainable community adaption of existing school or community projects.	23	3.74	20
19. I use strategies to secure funding and generate resources for a school community activity or project.	23	3.52	21

DISCUSSION

Further data analysis on the survey data was conducted using PSPPIRE Data Editor version GNU pspp 1.2.0-g0fb4db. Using the software, the instrument's Cronbach Alpha for all 21 items was determined to be 0.94. This shows high scale reliability and excellent internal consistency among the different action statements that measure perceptions of

teacher competency in community engagement. A copy of the exported output sheet for reliability testing is found on Appendix D.

To address the fourth objective of pilot testing, factor analysis using principal axis factoring was done through PSPPIRE Data Editor. This method was chosen for factor analysis because community engagement, as a construct, may be considered as a latent construct, thus it cannot be measured directly. In the initial extraction and rotation using 21 factors and 100 iterations, the total variance table showed five factors that had an Eigenvalue of more than 1.00. These five factors cumulatively account for 82.82% of the total variance. Having identified the factors that fit the Kaiser criterion, the second extraction and rotation using the Varimax method had five factors. The Total Variance Explained Table and the Rotated Factor Matrix are found on Appendix E.

Using 0.40 as the reference value for significance to identify the underlying factors that influence the perception of teachers in their community engagement competency, it was observed that multiple items were cross loaded across the five factors. At this load significance level, 11 items appear vague and need reconsiderations if it were to be included in the development of the second instrument prototype. Only three factors appear using 0.40 load significance level:

FACTOR 1	FACTOR 2	FACTOR 3
3. I build partnerships with diverse stakeholders (students, parents, businesses, NGOs, academics etc.) in the community to rally them in working for educational goals	2. I believe that I can positively contribute to the community by using my skills and applying my professional training as an educator	1. I understand of the context of my school community, as well the opportunities and social issues within it.
4. I communicate intentionally and clearly with different stakeholders.	7. I abide by the professional code of ethics in fulfilling my responsibilities to the school community.	
5. I have sufficient knowledge and training in managing a project.	14. I show respect to the people I work despite having different opinions, perspectives, and backgrounds.	
9. I am able to demonstrate my leadership skills in heading and participating in school community projects.	15. I consider how different stakeholders may be affected, either positively or negatively, by an action.	
10. I involve community stakeholders in class or school activities or projects to develop students' sense of community.		

Factor 1 may be labeled as Technical Skills, Factor 2 can be called Community Engagement Mindset, and Factor 3 may be named Ability to Contextualize. The rotated factor matrix with conditioned formatting for 0.40 loading significance is found in Appendix F.

Given the number of ambiguous items if Principal Axis Factoring is done at 0.40 loading significance, it is therefore necessary to evaluate the rotated factor matrix again at 0.55 load significance level. With this adjustment, cross loading among the different factors were eliminated and only one item, Question 16 on action orientation appears vague,

needs revision, or omission from the instrument. Five factors appear to influence the latent construct as shown by the table below:

FACTOR 1	FACTOR 2	FACTOR 3	FACTOR 4	FACTOR 5	DOES NOT LOAD
3. I build partnerships with diverse stakeholders (students, parents, businesses, NGOs, academics etc.) in the community to rally them in working for educational goals.	2. I believe that I can positively contribute to the community by using my skills and applying my professional training as an educator.	1. I understand of the context of my school community, as well the opportunities and social issues within it.	19. I use strategies to secure funding and generate resources for a school community activity or project.	8. I design lessons and do projects that are anchored on the community context.	16. I act accordingly to contribute to addressing the needs that I observe in my school community.
4. I communicate intentionally and clearly with different stakeholders.	7. I abide by the professional code of ethics in fulfilling my responsibilities to the school community.	21. I am transparent and accountable for all my actions.			
5. I have sufficient knowledge and training in managing a project.	14. I show respect to the people I work despite having different opinions, perspectives, and backgrounds.				
6. I participate in trainings that aim to develop community capabilities in doing community-based activities and projects for the school community.	15. I consider how different stakeholders may be affected, either positively or negatively, by an action.				
9. I am able to demonstrate my leadership skills in heading and participating in school community projects.					
10. I involve community stakeholders in class or school activities or projects to develop students' sense of community.					
11. I use different channels and mediums of communications to reach out to most, if not all, of the					

community stakeholders					
12. I am able to effectively plan, execute, and evaluate a school community activity or project.					
13. I plan for the sustainable community adaption of existing school or community projects.					
17. I take-on and share responsibilities for a community project with teammates or stakeholders.					
18. I am able to solicit feedback and sustain communications with partners regarding community concerns and projects.					
20. I inspire other people to initiate and join in activities and projects for the school community.					

These five factors may be labeled as: Factor 1 – Technical Skills, Factor 2 – Professionalism, Factor 3 – Social Awareness, Factor 4 – Resource Generation, and Factor 5 – Pedagogical Skills. The rotated factor matrix with conditioned formatting for 0.55 loading significance is found in Appendix G.

CONCLUSIONS

It can then be concluded that the result of Principal Axis Factoring with Varimax rotation reveals five factors influencing teachers' perception of their community engagement competency. These are technical skills, professionalism, social awareness, resource generation, and pedagogical skills. These five factors explain 82.82% of total variance. The initial seven categories of community engagement were trimmed down to five with one item, Question 16 on action orientation, for omission in the second instrument prototype.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Given the data gathered and analyzed from the pilot testing of the instrument to 23 teacher respondents, the following recommendations will be given priority in the development of the second instrument prototype:

1. Sampling. Sample size must be increased in proportion to the total target population. Given that the PPST and the RPMS are exclusively used for performance assessment in the public setting, the target population must also be further restricted to public school teachers serving in a region, city, municipality, or school. Increasing the sample size may also enable statistical analyses on segments of data as determined by demographic variables. For instance, mean scores may be compared between teachers who teach in the elementary and junior high school level.
2. Validity. The instrument may also need content validation from an expert.
3. Demographic variables. Instead of grouped variables for demographic data on years of service, input should be based on actual number of years in service per teacher. This may enable further statistical analyses such as correlating score mean and years in service.
4. Triangulation. Another round of call for volunteers may be done for a qualitative interview with the survey respondents to discuss their personal experiences in community engagement and the five factors that appear to influence the construct.
5. Instrument Revision. Omit Question 16 on action orientation and revise the instrument as a 20-item survey.

COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

The instrument prototype was converted to an online survey for pilot testing using Google Forms. Included in this are the initial agreement clauses for informed consent and voluntary participation in the study. With the given time restrictions for piloting the instrument prototype, an open online call for K-12 Filipino teachers who were teaching full-time or part-time last School Year 2019 – 2020 was launched through specialized teacher groups in Facebook between August 3 – 10, 2020. A total of 23 respondents from both public and private schools agreed to voluntarily answer the survey. Each respondent was given a code for confidentiality in the data processing and presentation.

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APPENDIX A: Demographic Profile Descriptive Statistics

SCHOOL TYPE	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cum Percent
Private	8	34.78	34.78	34.78
Public	15	65.22	65.22	100.00
Total	23	100.00	100.00	

TEACHING ASSIGNMENT LAST SCHOOL YEAR	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cum Percent
Elementary	8	34.78	34.78	34.78
Junior High School	7	30.43	30.43	65.22
Kinder	1	4.35	4.35	69.57
Senior High School	7	30.43	30.43	100.00
Total	23	100.00	100.00	

YEARS IN SERVICE (TEACHING)	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cum Percent
1 - 5 ye	15	65.22	65.22	65.22
11 – 15	3	13.04	13.04	78.26
21 – 25	1	4.35	4.35	82.61
6 - 10 y	4	17.39	17.39	100.00
Total	23	100.00	100.00	

APPENDIX B: Questionnaire Descriptive Statistics Per Item

QUESTION NUMBER	N	Mean	Var	Std Dev	Min	Max
1. I understand of the context of my school community, as well the opportunities and social issues within it.	23	4.48	0.51	0.73	2	5
2. I believe that I can positively contribute to the community by using my skills and applying my professional training as an educator.	23	4.65	0.31	0.57	3	5
3. I build partnerships with diverse stakeholders (students, parents, businesses, NGOs, academics etc.) in the community to rally them in working for educational goals.	23	4.26	0.54	0.75	2	5
4. I communicate intentionally and clearly with different stakeholders.	23	4	0.52	0.74	3	5
5. I have sufficient knowledge and training in managing a project.	23	4.04	0.91	0.98	2	5
6. I participate in trainings that aim to develop community capabilities in doing community-based activities and projects for the school community.	23	4.04	1.09	1.07	1	5
7. I abide by the professional code of ethics in fulfilling my responsibilities to the school community.	23	4.74	0.19	0.45	4	5
8. I design lessons and do projects that are anchored on the community context.	23	4.43	0.33	0.59	3	5
9. I am able to demonstrate my leadership skills in heading and participating in school community projects.	23	4	1.22	1.13	1	5
10. I involve community stakeholders in class or school activities or projects to develop students' sense of community.	23	4.22	0.95	1	1	5
11. I use different channels and mediums of communications to reach out to most, if not all, of the community stakeholders	23	4.26	0.63	0.81	3	5
12. I am able to effectively plan, execute, and evaluate a school community activity or project.	23	3.96	1.00	1.02	2	5
13. I plan for the sustainable community adaption of existing school or community projects.	23	3.74	1.24	1.14	1	5
14. I show respect to the people I work despite having different opinions, perspectives, and backgrounds.	23	4.74	0.28	0.54	3	5
15. I consider how different stakeholders may be affected, either positively or negatively, by an action.	23	4.61	0.33	0.58	3	5
16. I act accordingly to contribute to addressing the needs that I observe in my school community.	23	4.48	0.34	0.59	3	5
17. I take-on and share responsibilities for a community project with teammates or stakeholders.	23	4.26	0.80	0.92	1	5
18. I am able to solicit feedback and sustain communications with partners regarding community concerns and projects.	23	3.96	0.82	0.93	1	5
19. I use strategies to secure funding and generate resources for a school community activity or project.	23	3.52	1.47	1.24	1	5
20. I inspire other people to initiate and join in activities and projects for the school community.	23	3.96	0.82	0.93	2	5
21. I am transparent and accountable for all my actions.	23	4.65	0.40	0.65	3	5

APPENDIX C: Questionnaire Descriptive Statistics Average of All Items

Average of Self-Rating	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cum Percent
2.76	1	4.35	4.35	4.35
3.52	1	4.35	4.35	8.70
3.62	2	8.70	8.70	17.39
3.71	1	4.35	4.35	21.74
3.81	2	8.70	8.70	30.43
3.95	1	4.35	4.35	34.78
4.00	1	4.35	4.35	39.13
4.14	1	4.35	4.35	43.48
4.24	1	4.35	4.35	47.83
4.29	2	8.70	8.70	56.52
4.52	2	8.70	8.70	65.22
4.67	1	4.35	4.35	69.57
4.76	3	13.04	13.04	82.61
4.86	2	8.70	8.70	91.30
5.00	2	8.70	8.70	100.00
Total	23	100.00	100.00	

Mean	4.24
S.E. Mean	0.12
Mode	4.76
Std Dev	0.58
Variance	0.33
Kurtosis	0.13
S.E. Kurt	0.93
Skewness	-0.64
S.E. Skew	0.48
Range	2.24
Minimum	2.76
Maximum	5

APPENDIX D: Questionnaire Reliability

Cases	Valid	23	100
	Excluded	0	0
	Total	23	100

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.94	21

APPENDIX E: Questionnaire Factor Analysis using Principal Axis Factoring

TOTAL VARIANCE EXPLAINED						
Factor	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sum of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	10.07	47.97	47.97	10.07	47.96	47.96
2	3.35	15.94	63.91	3.35	15.94	63.9
3	1.7	8.08	71.99	1.7	8.07	71.97
4	1.18	5.62	77.61	1.18	5.61	77.58
5	1.09	5.21	82.82	1.09	5.21	82.79
6	0.78	3.73	86.55	0.78	3.71	86.5
7	0.58	2.76	89.31	0.58	2.76	89.26
8	0.5	2.38	91.7	0.5	2.38	91.63
9	0.4	1.9	93.6	0.4	1.9	93.53
10	0.33	1.56	95.16	0.33	1.55	95.09
11	0.25	1.18	96.34	0.25	1.17	96.26
12	0.24	1.12	97.47	0.23	1.11	97.37
13	0.18	0.86	98.32	0.18	0.85	98.22
14	0.14	0.67	99	0.14	0.67	98.89
15	0.12	0.58	99.58	0.12	0.58	99.47
16	0.05	0.21	99.8	0.04	0.21	99.68
17	0.03	0.13	99.93	0.03	0.12	99.8
18	0.01	0.05	99.98	0.01	0.04	99.85
19	0	0.02	100	0	0.01	99.85
20	0	0	100	0	0	99.85
21	0	0	100	0	0	99.85

ROTATED FACTOR MATRIX					
Questions	1	2	3	4	5
1. I understand of the context of my school community, as well the opportunities and social issues within it.	0.1	0.12	0.81	0.04	0.1
2. I believe that I can positively contribute to the community by using my skills and applying my professional training as an educator.	0.08	0.7	0.13	-0.17	-0.19
3. I build partnerships with diverse stakeholders (students, parents, businesses, NGOs, academics etc.) in the community to rally them in working for educational goals.	0.81	0.02	0.03	0.13	-0.06
4. I communicate intentionally and clearly with different stakeholders.	0.74	-0.02	0.25	-0.07	0.05
5. I have sufficient knowledge and training in managing a project.	0.79	0.16	0.18	0.13	0.23
6. I participate in trainings that aim to develop community capabilities in doing community-based activities and projects for the school community.	0.73	-0.2	0.1	0.4	0.22
7. I abide by the professional code of ethics in fulfilling my responsibilities to the school community.	0.11	0.74	0	-0.23	0.16
8. I design lessons and do projects that are anchored on the community context.	0.53	0.25	0.11	0.14	0.69
9. I am able to demonstrate my leadership skills in heading and participating in school community projects.	0.8	0.18	0.29	0.3	0.2
10. I involve community stakeholders in class or school activities or projects to develop students' sense of community.	0.8	0.17	-0.36	0.28	0.23
11. I use different channels and mediums of communications to reach out to most, if not all, of the community stakeholders	0.78	-0.06	-0.02	0.09	0.45
12. I am able to effectively plan, execute, and evaluate a school community activity or project.	0.71	0.26	0.25	0.16	0.41
13. I plan for the sustainable community adaption of existing school or community projects.	0.71	0.05	0.19	0.42	0.39
14. I show respect to the people I work despite having different opinions, perspectives, and backgrounds.	0.06	0.93	0.15	0.15	0.03
15. I consider how different stakeholders may be affected, either positively or negatively, by an action.	-0.1	0.73	0.08	0.16	0.16
16. I act accordingly to contribute to addressing the needs that I observe in my school community.	0.27	0.51	-0.08	0.43	0.36
17. I take-on and share responsibilities for a community project with teammates or stakeholders.	0.74	0.3	-0.29	0.44	-0.12
18. I am able to solicit feedback and sustain communications with partners regarding community concerns and projects.	0.57	0.05	0.1	0.5	-0.08
19. I use strategies to secure funding and generate resources for a school community activity or project.	0.42	-0.18	0.17	0.75	0.24
20. I inspire other people to initiate and join in activities and projects for the school community.	0.67	0.15	0.35	0.46	0.06
21. I am transparent and accountable for all my actions.	0.4	0.46	0.69	0.28	-0.1

APPENDIX F: Rotated Factor Matrix at 0.40 Loading Value

ROTATED FACTOR MATRIX					
Questions	1	2	3	4	5
1. I understand of the context of my school community, as well the opportunities and social issues within it.	0.1	0.12	0.81	0.04	0.1
2. I believe that I can positively contribute to the community by using my skills and applying my professional training as an educator.	0.08	0.7	0.13	-0.17	-0.19
3. I build partnerships with diverse stakeholders (students, parents, businesses, NGOs, academics etc.) in the community to rally them in working for educational goals.	0.81	0.02	0.03	0.13	-0.06
4. I communicate intentionally and clearly with different stakeholders.	0.74	-0.02	0.25	-0.07	0.05
5. I have sufficient knowledge and training in managing a project.	0.79	0.16	0.18	0.13	0.23
6. I participate in trainings that aim to develop community capabilities in doing community-based activities and projects for the school community.	0.73	-0.2	0.1	0.4	0.22
7. I abide by the professional code of ethics in fulfilling my responsibilities to the school community.	0.11	0.74	0	-0.23	0.16
8. I design lessons and do projects that are anchored on the community context.	0.53	0.25	0.11	0.14	0.69
9. I am able to demonstrate my leadership skills in heading and participating in school community projects.	0.8	0.18	0.29	0.3	0.2
10. I involve community stakeholders in class or school activities or projects to develop students' sense of community.	0.8	0.17	-0.36	0.28	0.23
11. I use different channels and mediums of communications to reach out to most, if not all, of the community stakeholders	0.78	-0.06	-0.02	0.09	0.45
12. I am able to effectively plan, execute, and evaluate a school community activity or project.	0.71	0.26	0.25	0.16	0.41
13. I plan for the sustainable community adaption of existing school or community projects.	0.71	0.05	0.19	0.42	0.39
14. I show respect to the people I work despite having different opinions, perspectives, and backgrounds.	0.06	0.93	0.15	0.15	0.03
15. I consider how different stakeholders may be affected, either positively or negatively, by an action.	-0.1	0.73	0.08	0.16	0.16
16. I act accordingly to contribute to addressing the needs that I observe in my school community.	0.27	0.51	-0.08	0.43	0.36
17. I take-on and share responsibilities for a community project with teammates or stakeholders.	0.74	0.3	-0.29	0.44	-0.12
18. I am able to solicit feedback and sustain communications with partners regarding community concerns and projects.	0.57	0.05	0.1	0.5	-0.08
19. I use strategies to secure funding and generate resources for a school community activity or project.	0.42	-0.18	0.17	0.75	0.24
20. I inspire other people to initiate and join in activities and projects for the school community.	0.67	0.15	0.35	0.46	0.06
21. I am transparent and accountable for all my actions.	0.4	0.46	0.69	0.28	-0.1

FACTOR 1	FACTOR 2	FACTOR 3	FACTOR 4	FACTOR 5	CROSS LOADING
3. I build partnerships with diverse stakeholders (students, parents, businesses, NGOs, academics etc.) in the community to rally them in working for educational goals	2. I believe that I can positively contribute to the community by using my skills and applying my professional training as an educator	1. I understand of the context of my school community, as well the opportunities and social issues within it.			6. I participate in trainings that aim to develop community capabilities in doing community-based activities and projects for the school community.
4. I communicate intentionally and clearly with different stakeholders.	7. I abide by the professional code of ethics in fulfilling my responsibilities to the school community.				8. I design lessons and do projects that are anchored on the community context.
5. I have sufficient knowledge and training in managing a project.	14. I show respect to the people I work despite having different opinions, perspectives, and backgrounds.				11. I use different channels and mediums of communications to reach out to most, if not all, of the community stakeholders
9. I am able to demonstrate my leadership skills in heading and participating in school community projects.	15. I consider how different stakeholders may be affected, either positively or negatively, by an action.				12. I am able to effectively plan, execute, and evaluate a school community activity or project.
10. I involve community stakeholders in class or school activities or projects to develop students' sense of community.					13. I plan for the sustainable community adaption of existing school or community projects.
					16. I act accordingly to contribute to addressing the needs that I observe in my school community.
					17. I take-on and share responsibilities for a community project with teammates or stakeholders.
					18. I am able to solicit feedback and sustain communications with partners regarding community concerns and projects.
					19. I use strategies to secure funding and generate resources for a school community activity or project.
					20. I inspire other people to initiate and join in activities and projects for the school community.
					21. I am transparent and accountable for all my actions.

APPENDIX G: Rotated Factor Matrix at 0.55 Loading Value

ROTATED FACTOR MATRIX					
Questions	1	2	3	4	5
1. I understand of the context of my school community, as well the opportunities and social issues within it.	0.1	0.12	0.81	0.04	0.1
2. I believe that I can positively contribute to the community by using my skills and applying my professional training as an educator.	0.08	0.7	0.13	-0.17	-0.19
3. I build partnerships with diverse stakeholders (students, parents, businesses, NGOs, academics etc.) in the community to rally them in working for educational goals.	0.81	0.02	0.03	0.13	-0.06
4. I communicate intentionally and clearly with different stakeholders.	0.74	-0.02	0.25	-0.07	0.05
5. I have sufficient knowledge and training in managing a project.	0.79	0.16	0.18	0.13	0.23
6. I participate in trainings that aim to develop community capabilities in doing community-based activities and projects for the school community.	0.73	-0.2	0.1	0.4	0.22
7. I abide by the professional code of ethics in fulfilling my responsibilities to the school community.	0.11	0.74	0	-0.23	0.16
8. I design lessons and do projects that are anchored on the community context.	0.53	0.25	0.11	0.14	0.69
9. I am able to demonstrate my leadership skills in heading and participating in school community projects.	0.8	0.18	0.29	0.3	0.2
10. I involve community stakeholders in class or school activities or projects to develop students' sense of community.	0.8	0.17	-0.36	0.28	0.23
11. I use different channels and mediums of communications to reach out to most, if not all, of the community stakeholders	0.78	-0.06	-0.02	0.09	0.45
12. I am able to effectively plan, execute, and evaluate a school community activity or project.	0.71	0.26	0.25	0.16	0.41
13. I plan for the sustainable community adaption of existing school or community projects.	0.71	0.05	0.19	0.42	0.39
14. I show respect to the people I work despite having different opinions, perspectives, and backgrounds.	0.06	0.93	0.15	0.15	0.03
15. I consider how different stakeholders may be affected, either positively or negatively, by an action.	-0.1	0.73	0.08	0.16	0.16
16. I act accordingly to contribute to addressing the needs that I observe in my school community.	0.27	0.51	-0.08	0.43	0.36
17. I take-on and share responsibilities for a community project with teammates or stakeholders.	0.74	0.3	-0.29	0.44	-0.12
18. I am able to solicit feedback and sustain communications with partners regarding community concerns and projects.	0.57	0.05	0.1	0.5	-0.08
19. I use strategies to secure funding and generate resources for a school community activity or project.	0.42	-0.18	0.17	0.75	0.24
20. I inspire other people to initiate and join in activities and projects for the school community.	0.67	0.15	0.35	0.46	0.06
21. I am transparent and accountable for all my actions.	0.4	0.46	0.69	0.28	-0.1

FACTOR 1	FACTOR 2	FACTOR 3	FACTOR 4	FACTOR 5	DOES NOT LOAD
3. I build partnerships with diverse stakeholders (students, parents, businesses, NGOs, academics etc.) in the community to rally them in working for educational goals.	2. I believe that I can positively contribute to the community by using my skills and applying my professional training as an educator.	1. I understand of the context of my school community, as well the opportunities and social issues within it.	19. I use strategies to secure funding and generate resources for a school community activity or project.	8. I design lessons and do projects that are anchored on the community context.	16. I act accordingly to contribute to addressing the needs that I observe in my school community.
4. I communicate intentionally and clearly with different stakeholders.	7. I abide by the professional code of ethics in fulfilling my responsibilities to the school community.	21. I am transparent and accountable for all my actions.			
5. I have sufficient knowledge and training in managing a project.	14. I show respect to the people I work despite having different opinions, perspectives, and backgrounds.				
6. I participate in trainings that aim to develop community capabilities in doing community-based activities and projects for the school community.	15. I consider how different stakeholders may be affected, either positively or negatively, by an action.				
9. I am able to demonstrate my leadership skills in heading and participating in school community projects.					
10. I involve community stakeholders in class or school activities or projects to develop students' sense of community.					
11. I use different channels and mediums of communications to reach out to most, if not all, of the community stakeholders					
12. I am able to effectively plan, execute, and evaluate a school community activity or project.					
13. I plan for the sustainable community adaption of existing school or community projects.					
17. I take-on and share responsibilities for a community project with teammates or stakeholders.					
18. I am able to solicit feedback and sustain communications with partners regarding community concerns and projects.					
20. I inspire other people to initiate and join in activities and projects for the school community.					